

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**
Project 'SIMPLE'

Deliverable D1.5
Final report

Due date of deliverable: M57
Actual submission date: 14.01.2025

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EJP SOIL

Project title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Project website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020

Project duration: 60 months

Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER:	D1.5
DELIVERABLE TITLE:	Final report
DELIVERABLE TYPE:	Report
WORK PACKAGE N:	WP1
WORK PACKAGE TITLE:	Coordination
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DOI:	10.5281/zenodo.14645396
LICENSE:	CC BY 4.0
DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	PU

ABSTRACT

Reducing the environmental impacts of agriculture, as envisaged by the Farm to Fork strategy, may have benefits and trade-offs that need to be identified and quantified. The EJP SOIL project SIMPLE (Scenario modelling for assessing impacts of policy changes and socio-economic effects on ecosystem services of soils) combined different European data sources and modelling approaches for the EU and neighbouring countries to assess the impact of key elements of the Farm to Fork strategy on soil-related ecosystem services crop yield, nitrogen (N) emissions and soil organic carbon (SOC) storage. For the policy element considered most important in SIMPLE, a generic 20 % reduction in mineral N fertilisation, an average yield reduction of 9-10 % is estimated for major arable crops (19 % for rapeseed). The yield response estimates are plausible but associated with large uncertainties. Lower crop yields are associated with lower crop residues, which on average reduce SOC stocks in European mineral cropland soils by 0.9 t ha⁻¹ over 30 years. This finding is worrying as a case study from Sweden showed a positive relationship between SOC content and maize yields, underlining the role of SOC for soil fertility. The effect of reduced N fertilisation on root biomass is less clear, with either no or slightly reduced numbers. The 20 % reduction in mineral N fertilizer use for main arable crops resulted on average in 15 % lower N₂O emissions and 24 % lower N leaching and runoff. N fertilisation may also depend on fertiliser prices, which in turn are scaled with the price of fossil fuels. The corresponding study in SIMPLE showed that higher prices reduce fertiliser use only to a small extent.

Two other elements of agricultural policy have been addressed: a change in diet towards more plant-based foods and an increase in the share of organic farming. An increase in the number of vegetarians leads to shifts in the composition of livestock and, on average, reduces the number of animals and the amount of animal products. However, the reduction in N emissions is small. Organic farming is expected to experience a decrease in yield, which could be compensated at the European level by the reactivation of currently abandoned land, especially in Central and Eastern Europe.

Using the SOMMIT index developed in another EJP SOIL project, which allows a quantitative assessment of the trade-offs among ecosystem services showed that implementing a 20 % reduction in N fertilisation will have positive aggregated effects for some crops and regions (i.e. environmental impacts from N losses are decreased without large yield or SOC losses). However, the results for other crops and regions indicate significant negative impacts (either small environmental improvements or large yield/SOC losses). Therefore, implementing policy changes such as reduced N fertilisation carries risks for crop production and SOC storage.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
SOC	Soil organic carbon
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
NO ₃	Nitrate

1. Introduction

Agricultural soils provide a wide array of ecosystem services that need to be maintained and enhanced if agriculture is to be made more sustainable and climate friendly. The goal of SIMPLE was to simultaneously set up a tool to assess the impact of policy changes and socio-economic effects on three such ecosystem services. For this purpose, we set up a modelling framework to quantify changes in yields, soil carbon storage and nitrous oxide emissions at the European scale. This large-scale modelling approach was complemented by more detailed studies on specific aspects of the above-mentioned soil functions or that focus on smaller regions. This report summarizes all work packages of SIMPLE and gives an overview of the entire project outcome.

The modelling framework is described in Chapter 2.1. Our analysis focused on potential effects of the Farm to Fork strategy, which is a central element of the Green Deal. One important aim of this strategy is to reduce nutrient losses by 50% as these are associated with air, soil and water pollution, loss of biodiversity and greenhouse gas emissions. Reducing mineral fertilization by at least 20 % by 2030 is an important element of the corresponding policy (Farm to Fork). However, this could lead to trade-offs in terms of yields and soil carbon storage. In SIMPLE we quantified the effect of -20 % reduced mineral nitrogen fertilization by focusing on the six most important crops grown in Europe. In chapter 2.2 we present potential yield reductions that could result from lower N fertilization. Soil organic carbon stocks could be directly affected by lower yields as the amount of crop residues may be reduced and these are important carbon inputs to the soil. This part of the work builds on the EJP SOIL project CarboSeq and is discussed in Chapter 2.3. Whether reduced fertilization will uniformly lower N losses is quantified in chapter 2.4. In chapter 2.5. we assessed how the Farm to Fork strategy could affect soils through changes in land use. In chapter 2.1.2 and 2.1.3 we describe two other socio-economic impacts, namely changes in fertilizer prices and changes in diets, that could affect fertilization rates and could be assessed using such a modelling framework. The chapters on soil organic carbon and land use include case studies for Flanders (2.3.3 and 2.5.3). Finally, chapter 2.6 demonstrates how to analyse the effect of reduced fertilization on different ecosystem services simultaneously by applying the SOMMIT index, a tool developed in the EJP SOIL project of the same name.

2. Results

2.1. Framework and results from scenario modelling

A modelling framework was set up by combining the widely used Rothamsted soil carbon model RothC with the agricultural economic model AGMEMOD (AGricultural MEMber states MODelling) and the nitrogen flow model MITERRA-Europe. The latter two models have already been linked in the recent H2020 project SUPREMA. Yields for baseline conditions were collected from FAO statistics. To estimate changes in response to reduced fertilization equations and data were collected from the literature and from EJP SOIL partners (see 2.2.).

One of the main challenges of setting up the modelling framework was the strong dependency of simulations on results from other models/statistics. Additional challenges were the different spatial resolutions used (e.g. MITERRA-Europe uses NUTS2 and RothC is set up on a 10x10 km grid). Furthermore, we wanted to focus on the effect of reduced fertilization on the most important main crops on arable land, but not all models are designed to produce crop-specific output (e.g. MITERRA-Europe).

2.1.1 Impact of Farm to Fork fertilizer use reduction

This study provides some insights regarding the potential impacts of reducing mineral N fertilisation by 20% in the case of selected major cash crops: wheat, rapeseed, sugar beet, maize and barley (Gonzalez-Martinez and Keel 2025). In terms of the geographical scope, the analysis focuses on the EU27 and the United Kingdom (UK). Regarding the methodology, a forward-looking scenario covering the period 2021-2030 has been simulated by means of AGMEMOD.

In general terms, the decline in fertiliser use could induce a decline in crop yields (unless overfertilisation occurs), while the related decline in production is expected to lead to an increase in the prices of the relevant crops. In addition, the reduction in fertiliser application is likely to affect the quality of agricultural production, leading to lower prices at farm-gate level. The net price effect will depend on the size and direction of these opposing impacts, i.e. price increase due to scarcity versus price decline due to quality deterioration. As shown in the scenario simulation, the achievement of the intended 20% reduction in N fertilization is expected to result in lower productivity (yields), and subsequently, lower production volumes. Lower supplied volumes affect export patterns, as well as food self-sufficiency rates. According to the simulation the strongest declines in self-sufficiency rates are projected in the case of rapeseed and barley.

A final remark regarding the interpretation of the outcomes of this modelling exercise is due. A comprehensive assessment of the implications of the Farm-to-Fork and Biodiversity strategies would require a much more complex modelling exercise in which exogenous shocks on a broader set of activities, e.g. other crops and livestock farming, together with additional policy measures and further price dynamics, e.g. reflecting quality deterioration and/or scarcity due to lower production, should be also included. Nevertheless, the results of this study are still insightful since they can help us to understand the potential implications of lower productivity in the agricultural sector. These remarks are still informative for policymakers when developing policies to ensure/foster economic and environmental sustainability of farming activities.

2.1.2 Effect of increasing fertilizer prices

We assessed how changes in fertilizer prices affect the consumption of fertilizers and agricultural production (Miaris et al. 2024). We present three case studies: (1) for the European Union (EU), (2) for Sweden, and (3) for Switzerland. For the EU case study, we rely on country-level data from 24 EU countries. For the Swedish case, we use regional-level data from 21 Swedish regions and for the Swiss case, we use the Information System of Structural Change in Switzerland/StrukturWandel InformationsSystem Schweiz (SWISSland) model.

The results of the EU case study show that EU farmers rely to a large extent on mineral nitrogen fertilizers, with no signs of gradual reduction as consumption fluctuates periodically over the past 22 years. Moreover, farmers' consumption is 'inelastic' to changes in fertilizer prices, i.e. a 10% increase in the value of mineral nitrogen fertilizer prices would reduce mineral nitrogen fertilizer consumption in the EU by only approximately 1%, indicating a strong dependency on mineral nitrogen fertilizers. However, the level of dependency can vary according to the geographic and climatic characteristics of the agricultural system. The Swedish case confirms the findings from the EU, with Swedish farmers exhibiting a similar relationship between fertilizer consumption and price changes (Gonzalez-Martinez and Miaris 2024). The results of the Swiss case study show that projected changes in fertilizer prices do not significantly impact agricultural production, as fertilizer costs constitute only a small share of total farm costs. However, a substantial increase in fertilizer prices (e.g., a tenfold increase) does raise farming costs and subsequently impacts agricultural production.

2.1.3 Effect of changing human diets

This study analyses how dietary changes can impact nitrogen inputs to and losses from the soil through changes in agricultural production including changes in crop area, livestock numbers, foreign trade and manure application for crops (Djanibekov et al. 2025). We present two case studies: (1) all countries of the European Union (EU) and (2) Switzerland. For the EU-level case study which focuses on a reduction in meat consumption, we rely on the outcomes of a literature review and on previous work undertaken by the Agriculture Member State Modelling (AGMEMOD) and MITERRA modelling teams in the context of the H2020 SUPREMA (Support for Policy Relevant Modelling of Agriculture) project. For the case of Switzerland, effects of healthier diets are quantified using the Swiss sustainable food systems (SWISSfoodSys) model.

The results of the European Union case study show that the dietary changes reduce livestock numbers, production and prices of animal-based products. The reduction of livestock numbers, however, only marginally decreases GHG emissions, with impacts differing across regions. The results of the Swiss case study show that dietary changes impact the entire food system including agricultural production, processing and trade. A substantial consumption shift towards vegetables, fruits and grains is observed, while the consumption of meat and alcoholic beverages is substantially lower. These changes increase the area where grains, vegetables and fruits are grown, while the area of fodder crops (i.e. feed like silage maize) and meadows are smaller. As a result of lower feed availability, total livestock number is reduced, leading to lower amounts of manure. Both case studies demonstrate the direct link between changes in diets and nitrogen availability. We conclude that moving towards healthier diets including lower meat consumption, however, reduces nitrogen losses only to a small extent.

2.2. Changes in yields at the European scale

2.2.1 Analysis of national yield statistics and yield response to reduced fertilization

The effect of –20 % lower N fertilization rates on yields for the most important crop types in Europe, Turkey and Switzerland was determined based on yield statistics, fertilization recommendations and fertilizer response functions (Madenoglu et al. 2024). The estimated yield reduction was highest for rapeseed (19 % on average). For all other crops (wheat, barley, maize, potato, sugar beet) it was between 9 and 10 %.

2.2.2 Yield response to SOC

The mechanisms through which soil organic carbon (SOC) concentration affects crop yields are numerous but difficult to separate. The objective of this Swedish study was to disentangle these processes and estimate to what extent the yield response to SOC is mainly driven by changes in soil physical or biochemical properties and processes (Kätterer and Bolinder 2024). This was achieved by analysing the response of yields in continuous maize cropping systems during 20 years (2000-2019) to differences in SOC concentrations, ranging from 0.94% to 3.65% in the topsoil (0–20 cm), which had evolved in 14 experimental treatments in a Swedish long-term field experiment at Ultuna that was initiated in 1956. Average maize yields during this period varied between 1.9 and 8.4 Mg dry mass per hectare in the different treatments. Our analysis showed that maize yield in the treatments that were not severely limited by nitrogen supply or soil acidity increased by 16% for each percentage unit increase in SOC. Two thirds of the yield increase in response to SOC change could be ascribed to associated changes in soil physical properties. Our analysis suggests that the extra storage capacity of water was the main driver for the observed yield responses. We conclude that measures for increasing SOC in soils most likely are an effective adaptation strategy for reducing the

risk of crop damage during dry spells, which probably are becoming more frequent in the future due to climate change, even in relatively humid climates as in Sweden.

2.3. Changes in soil organic carbon stocks at the European scale

The objective of this part of SIMPLE was to assess the impact of different scenarios of sustainable agriculture in Europe on organic carbon in agricultural soils. Soil carbon is a key indicator for soil health and fertility and can be directly influenced by agricultural management. We assessed how agricultural policies may impact the future development of soil carbon stocks in European croplands. The impact of two goals of the Farm to Fork strategy, reduced fertilization (-20%) and increased share of organic farming, was explored in different scenarios.

2.3.1 Fertilization effects on C input to soils

Yield and the associated net primary productivity of crops determines the amount of above- and belowground plant C input to soils, which in turn affects how soil organic C (SOC) stocks evolve in different agroecosystems. The belowground C inputs are particularly important since their contribution to the formation of more stable SOC is higher than that from aboveground crop residues. The objective of this task was to examine the effect of a reduction in N fertilization, which is usually the most important yield-limiting factor, on plant C input to soils. For that purpose, we conducted a literature review and measured root biomass in German field trials.

2.3.1.1 Literature review on the effect of N fertilization on root biomass

We conducted a literature review on the effect of N fertilization on root biomass at or close to crop maturity, and we briefly discuss the concepts involved in estimating annual C input to soils from yields using allometric functions (Bolinder & Kätterer, 2024). Data from 25 references (N = 148) allowed us to make different types of paired comparisons for total root biomass between several mineral N treatments (including zero controls) and for different crop categories. The mean effect using data from all crop categories combined showed no significant effect of a reduced N fertilization on root biomass for none of the different types of comparisons. Only when analyzed separately (e.g., small-grain cereals) and for the extreme comparisons such as those involving zero N controls were significant. The number of observations is limited and associated with considerable variability. It also remains difficult to investigate whether C inputs from roots are related to crop yields or total aboveground production because all these components are rarely measured simultaneously in the studies. In our review, we were only able to test this on a subset of data (N = 20) for wheat and barley and found a good correlation for root biomass with both yield and total aboveground biomass. However, in the context of estimating the effect of a reduction in N fertilization (and thereby of a reduction in crop productivity) on plant C input to soils, many of the available allometric functions consider the amount of C inputs from roots are positively influenced by crop productivity. These allometric functions differ (i.e., a given yield-reduction does not produce the same estimated difference in root biomass); consequently, the choice of the allometric function used will influence the estimated effect of a reduction in N fertilization in C input. Furthermore, we highlight that using a yield-scaled harvest index associated with the allometric functions can also affect estimated belowground C inputs.

2.3.1.2 Effect of reduced N fertilization on root biomass in German field trials

We sampled root biomass in 19 fertilization field trials across Germany that reduced N-fertilization rates by 20 %. Samples were collected after harvest in the year 2023. In winter wheat, root biomass was reduced by 9 % on average. In winter barley, a similar trend was detected, though it was not

statistically significant. The root biomass of silage maize and winter rapeseed was not affected by a 20 % reduction of N-fertilization.

2.3.2 European-scale simulations of reduced mineral N fertilization

In this task it was assessed how a 20 % reduction in nitrogen (N) fertilization affects soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks across Europe using the RothC model (Pape 2024). The simulations are run across Europe on a 10x10 km grid (aligned with EJP SOIL CarboSeq project). The SOC levels depend on the balance between carbon inputs (from plants) and carbon outputs (due to mineralization). Lower N fertilization reduces crop yields, which decreases carbon inputs and ultimately lowers SOC stocks.

The study estimates SOC losses over 30 years using yield reduction data and different allocation models for crop residues and roots.

The SOC losses vary across European countries, with Czechia experiencing the highest SOC loss per hectare, largely due to wheat and rapeseed cultivation (Figure 1).

On average, over the 30-year period European agricultural land loses 0.928 t SOC/ha due to reduced N fertilization, with wheat accounting for the largest share of this loss (0.353 t C/ha), followed by rapeseed (0.220 t C/ha) and maize (0.207 t C/ha).

Figure 1. Soil organic carbon loss after 30 years from six main arable crops if 20 % less mineral N fertilizer is applied. The unit is SOC loss in tons per hectare of agricultural land in the 10x10 km grid cell. Hence, the actual size of agricultural land in the grid cell is not taken into account but only the loss of the average hectare, be it one hectare in that grid cell or 10,000. The loss is a function of yield level, yield reduction, share of agricultural land where the crop is grown and the humification coefficient. Maize includes grain and silage maize.

The SOC loss is influenced by factors such as the crop's share of agricultural land, yield reduction, and local mineralization conditions, which are affected mainly by climate.

SOC losses may be underestimated for some countries where the six crops analysed only cover a small portion of total agricultural land. Estimated SOC losses are higher than average in countries with a larger share of high-yielding crops in their agricultural area.

2.3.3 Case study for Flanders

The impact of fodder crop changes on the soil organic carbon stocks in Flanders (Belgium) was assessed (Mertens et al. 2024). In the investigated scenario the composition of cattle feed was adjusted. Silage maize is the most common fodder crop and generally the most common crop grown in Flanders. However, silage maize does not have a high contribution to the SOC storage in arable soils compared to other crops due to low amounts of crop residues left in the field after harvest. Cereals and legumes, such as winter barley and clover, on the other hand are known to have a positive impact on SOC storage. Since silage maize is the most grown fodder crop and not many farmers will be willing or able to convert all of their fields to cereals or legumes, it was decided to run a scenario in which silage maize is replaced by winter barley, with the straw removed after harvest, on 10% of the parcels where it is currently cultivated.

The impact of the shift in crops was simulated with a Roth-C based model developed specifically for Flanders (BeSOCC model). The model was initially developed to be used as a digital tool for farmers (UGent and BDB, 2006; Verlinden et al., 2013; Beirinckx et al. 2023) and uses a simplified initialisation method.

Each rotation year 10% of all the parcels in Flanders with silage maize were randomly selected to be replaced by winter barley. The scenario was compared with a business-as-usual (BAU) scenario. The simulations were performed at parcel-level and afterwards aggregated to NUTS3 level. The results indicate that a slight increase of the SOC storage of, on average, $0.013 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ will occur in all NUTS3 areas if there is a shift in the fodder crops cultivated.

2.4. Nitrogen losses from agricultural soils

2.4.1 Updating input data for the MITERRA-Europe model

The MITERRA-Europe model is used in the EJP Soil SIMPLE project to simulate the impact of reduced mineral fertilizer use on nitrogen emissions. MITERRA-Europe is a deterministic emission and nutrient flow model, which calculates greenhouse gas (CO_2 , CH_4 and N_2O) emissions, nitrogen emissions (N_2O , NH_3 , NO_x and NO_3), N and P flows and soil organic carbon stock changes on annual basis, using emission factors and leaching fractions (Velthof et al., 2009; Lesschen et al., 2011; Velthof et al., 2014). In collaboration with the HorizonEurope project NutriBudget, the model was updated to the most recent activity data for the year 2020. In addition, the model was expanded to Switzerland and Turkey, countries involved in EJP Soil, but currently not covered in the model. Finally, it was not possible to fully include Turkey as too many input data were missing, especially soil data were not available, as Turkey is not part of the European Soil Database and not included in the LUCAS soil surveys.

2.4.2 Including CN interactions in the model

As part of Task 5.2 we improved the carbon nitrogen interactions in MITERRA-Europe, which were until now not linked. To do so, we included the Nitrogen component in RothC (Coleman and Jenkinson, 2014), which was already part of MITERRA-Europe. The RothCN model is developed based on the principals of the classic RothC model, and links soil organic nitrogen (SON) turnover with soil organic carbon (SOC) decomposition using C:N ratios. For the SOC part, RothCN is mostly identical to RothC, except that RothCN considers plant residues and manure as separate input material categories. Input materials are partitioned into decomposable and resistant compartments. An additional humified manure material compartment (HMA) is set up to hold the fraction of already decomposed manure (see Figure 2). Each compartment decomposes following a first-order reaction kinetics, and is converted to microbial biomass (BIO), humus material (HUM), and CO_2 . To model SON

turnover, each compartment is assigned a C:N ratio, which is used to determine the N released from organic matter decomposition. Different C:N ratios may be assigned for plant residue and manure compartments to account for their differences in N content. N assimilated into BIO and HUM compartments are also calculated according to their respective C:N ratios. The difference between total N release and N assimilation determines whether net N mineralization or immobilization should take place. In the case of mineralization, the mineralized N is added to the soil inorganic N pool and made available for crop uptake and soil processes (not modelled by RothCN). If immobilization should take place, RothCN will first check if the soil inorganic N pool is sufficient for immobilization requirement and then determines if decomposition should be reduced in case of N source insufficiency. The RothCN model is embedded in the MITERRA-Europe model, and the SON turnover is therefore coupled with crop N uptake and N losses modelled by MITERRA-Europe.

Figure 2. Schematic overview of the carbon and nitrogen pools in RothCN.

2.4.3 Assessing the impact of Farm to Fork scenarios on nitrogen losses

For the assessment of the impact of the Farm to Fork scenarios on nitrogen losses we used two approaches (Lesschen et al. 2025). The first approach was specifically focussed on the reduction of mineral N fertilizer use for the six main arable crops in Europe (wheat, barley, maize, rapeseed, potato and sugar beet). This approach was aligned with the estimated yield reductions (Chapter 2.2) and changes in soil organic carbon stocks (Chapter 2.3). However, for the yield impacts, we had to make a correction for the use of organic fertilizers. Although mineral fertilizer is the main source of N input, on average 70%, see Figure 3, the input of nitrogen from manure can be more than 50% of the total N input in some livestock dense regions. Therefore, the yield reduction was reduced according to the share of organic N fertilizer.

Figure 3. Average N input and source per crop for EU-28 countries

With MITERRA-Europe first a baseline simulation was performed with the activity data of the year 2020, which was compared with the simulation of the scenario in which mineral N fertilizer use per crop was reduced by 20%. The results were compared and are available at NUTS2 level, which are used in the trade-off/synthesis assessment of WP7 of SIMPLE, and at national / EU level. Soil N₂O emissions comprise all emissions from direct (mineral fertilizer, organic fertilizer, crop residues) and indirect (volatilisation and leaching) emission sources. The 20% reduction in mineral N fertilizer use resulted on average in 15% lower N₂O emissions. The total emission reduction for these six crops in the EU-28 countries is about 27 kton N₂O, which is about 7.3 Mton CO₂-eq, based on the AR6 GWP value of 273 for N₂O. Based on the work in WP4 (Chapter 2.3) the average loss of soil carbon due to the lower mineral N fertilization was about 0.11 ton CO₂/ha/year (0.928 ton C/ha over 30 years). The average reduction in N₂O emissions was 0.13 ton CO₂-eq/ha/year, which is slightly higher compared to the loss of carbon. From a climate mitigation point of view, the reduction in N₂O emissions as resulting from reduced N fertilization is thus not offset by the loss of soil carbon, and as the carbon losses will decrease over time, the net climate benefit will increase.

The reduction in total N leaching and runoff for these six crops was even larger and on average reduced by 24% for the EU-28. However, this varied amongst countries from 8% to 33% reduction, depending on the share of mineral fertilizer and the current N surplus. Reduced mineral N fertilization will therefore have positive impacts on N losses, with net climate mitigation benefits and improvements of ground and surface water quality in the EU.

2.5. Land use changes

Since 2000, changes in total agricultural lands in Europe have been marginal, as a slight increase in croplands is accompanied by a slight decrease in permanent meadows and pastures (FAO, 2023). In Europe, agricultural lands have a bigger share of croplands to meadows and pastures; within croplands, the share of herbaceous crops increased.

2.5.1 Impact of Farm to Fork strategy on land use

Implementing the farm-to-fork strategy may impact the agricultural landscape in Europe in multiple ways, as defined goals tackle several spheres, from the environment to dietary preferences to food security (Billen et al., 2021; Rööß et al., 2022). One of the most challenging goals is reducing N application (Zira et al., 2021). Combined with an increased share of organic agriculture, it may

pressure Europe's existing land use structure. The precise impact on land-use change is difficult to predict. From the biophysical perspective, Europe has sufficient resources to reach its goals if changes in meat consumption would be combined with legume cultivation, recycling of human excreta and interlinkage of livestock and crop production for efficient use of manure. Therefore, goals may be reached without changes in land use (Billen et al., 2021). However, the precise impact on land-use change is difficult to predict.

Storyline modelling research suggests that achieving the target of the farm-to-fork and other EU policies (biodiversity) is within reach. We can make significant strides towards these goals by embracing biodiversity-based and agroecological solutions and transforming the current farming system (Röös et al., 2022). However, it is crucial to understand that these goals can only be realised through significant societal changes, changes in diets, taxation, and other activities.

In addition, the precise pattern of these changes also may be shifted and corrected through future technological progress (Purnhagen et al., 2021), as well as political and socio-economic practices (Wesseler, 2022).

2.5.2 Impact of changes in diet and increasing share of organic farming

European diets do not follow dietary recommendations - the average intake of red meat exceeds recommendations, while the consumption of whole grains, fruits, vegetables, legumes and nuts is insufficient (European Commission 2020). The EU's Farm to Fork strategy outlines the impact of a more plant-based diet, with less red and processed meat and more fruit and vegetables (European Commission 2020). The most significant shift in diet is between red meat and legume calorie intake (Purnhagen et al., 2021). However, the impact of dietary changes on land-use is difficult to quantify (Wesseler 2022), as exports can compensate for the loss of the domestic market. Similarly, international trade may offset expected local environmental benefits (Guillaume et al., 2024). At the same time, we need to consider possible impacts from the increase in demand for animal-source food in the developing countries as they become wealthier (Alexandratos & Bruinsma, 2012). Possible changes in agricultural land management may include an increase in organic agricultural land from just under 10% to at least 25% of total EU agricultural land (European Commission 2020). Conversion of conventional agricultural land to organic farming can result in yield losses (Clemens et al. 2021) of between 20% and 35%, as mentioned in some studies (Boix-Fayos & de Vente, 2023), creating a need for additional land conversion to maintain the previous harvest volume (Purnhagen et al., 2021).

In combination, reduced consumption and production of animal products would reduce the competition between land for animal feed (Boix-Fayos, de Vente 2023) and human food, in turn increasing the land available for organic agriculture for human consumption (Boix-Fayos, de Vente 2023). In terms of pasture, there would be a shift from intensively to extensively used grassland, with the latter taking over more land (Guillaume et al., 2024). In order to replace animal proteins for human consumption, the use of land for legumes (soya, pulses) would increase, using land that was previously used for cereals (Guillaume et al., 2024).

2.5.3 Detailed case study for Flanders: assess impact of less livestock and change in diet on soil organic carbon

In this second case study for Flanders (Belgium), the impact of an adjustment in the composition of cattle feed on SOC stocks was investigated (Mertens et al. 2024). Silage maize is the most common fodder crop, and even the most common crop cultivated in Flanders. However, silage maize does not have a high contribution to the SOC storage in arable soils compared to some other crops, such as cereals and fodder legumes. In this study, we have investigated the impact on SOC stocks of replacing silage maize by winter barley, with straw residues removed after harvest, on 10 % of the parcels where it is currently cultivated. The impact of the shift in fodder crops was simulated with a Roth-C based model. The Belgian Soil Organic Carbon Calculator (BeSOCC) integrates the Roth-C

model, with an approach for the initialisation and the calculation of carbon inputs by crops and fertilization developed specifically for Belgium, Flanders that builds further on earlier work for developing a digital decision support tool for farmers to simulate the evolution of the SOC in arable land. The scenario was compared with a business-as-usual (BAU) scenario. The BAU scenario was developed based on the management data of 5 years (2018-2022). Due to missing crop and fertilization data, simulations could be performed for 52.3% of the arable fields. The simulations were performed at parcel-level and afterwards aggregated to NUTS3 level. The results indicate that an increase of the SOC storage will occur in all NUTS3 areas if there is a shift in the fodder crops. This increase is on average $0.013 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and ranges between 0.003 and $0.025 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

2.5.4 Driving factors of land-use and spatial relationships

The dynamics of land use change are influenced by a complex interplay of social, economic, political, technological and biophysical factors (Hersperger & Bürgi, 2009), each contributing to regional variations in agricultural practices and sustainability.

Economic drivers are pivotal in dictating land use transformations through market forces, industrialization, and agricultural policies (van Vliet et al. 2015). The patterns of intensification and extensification are influenced by these economic factors, as observed in the systematic review of agricultural land use change in Europe conducted by Hersperger & Bürgi (2009), which reveals trends toward both intensification and deintensification in response to market demands. Urbanization typically contributes to intensified land use in metropolitan areas while promoting extensification in rural settings, reflecting the dual pressures of economic growth and population dynamics.

Additionally, global trade and agricultural policies significantly affect land use patterns, particularly in relation to land abandonment and the sustainability of agricultural practices (Valujeva, Debernardini, et al., 2022).

Economic needs are strongly related to political processes, policies, and regulations; therefore, they are interlinked with political factors and play a critical role in shaping land use outcomes. Production of biofuels through policies and economic demand are an example (Persson, 2013; Rulli et al., 2016). Agricultural subsidies, both nationally and from the European Union, are instrumental in maintaining agricultural operations and preserving landscapes, albeit with challenges for long-term sustainability (Rendenieks et al., 2020; Ruskule et al., 2013).

Social factors, such as population dynamics and culturally-specific norms, significantly shape land utilization, particularly in rural areas (Leal Filho et al., 2017; Liechti & Biber, 2016; Maurer et al., 2006). The demand for agricultural land and housing is affected by demographic shifts and ingrained cultural practices, which dictate land use patterns. Biophysical factors, including soil fertility, topography, and climate, fundamentally shape land use decisions (Wiesmeier et al., 2019). Fertile soils often lead to intensified agricultural practices, while less productive lands may be designated for extensive uses, like grazing. The topographical characteristics of an area influence its land use. Climatic conditions further impact land management

2.5.4.1 Intensification

Agricultural land intensification is characterized by, e.g., higher livestock density and mechanization, along with the expansion of agricultural areas, reduced landscape diversity, and specialization of agricultural activities. In increased management intensity (Van Vliet et al. 2015). The drivers of intensification are complex, with technological and institutional factors being the most frequently cited. Economic and location-related influences play a moderate role, while demographic and sociocultural factors show limited impact. Notably, farmer characteristics and the economic conditions of farming families are significant, especially regarding specialization in agricultural activities.

2.5.4.2 Extensification

Agricultural land abandonment is a critical issue in Europe, particularly pronounced in post-socialist Central and Eastern European countries. The transition to a market-oriented economy and EU policy implementation has led to the abandonment of lower-quality soils in remote areas. During the transition period, demographic changes significantly influenced this trend, while fewer factors played a role during EU accession (Pazúr et al., 2014).

A review of over 140 studies indicates that land abandonment and extensification account for 62% of landscape changes (Plieninger et al., 2016). While abandonment can enhance biodiversity, it poses risks to traditional agricultural landscapes and ecosystem services (Lasanta et al., 2017). Projections estimate that by 2040, between 71,277 and 211,814 km² of agricultural land may be abandoned, revealing urgent needs for intervention. An assessment identified trade-offs involving losses in agriculture-related values, but also potential benefits like increased carbon sequestration (van der Zanden et al., 2017).

These findings have critical implications for land use policy. Effective interventions are necessary to sustain productive agricultural lands and conserve those undergoing significant changes. In regions like Central and Eastern Europe, the mixed trends of intensification and deintensification highlight underutilized opportunities for improving food security and enhancing ecosystem services. Reintegrating abandoned agricultural land into production is a potential pathway to meet the aspirations of the Common Agriculture Policy post-2020, emphasizing the need for balanced policies that promote productivity alongside ecological sustainability.

2.5.5 Land-use change effects on soil properties and ecosystem services

Originally the aim of SIMPLE was to quantify changes in SOC stocks associated with changes in land-use (e.g. conversion from grassland to cropland) as a result of reduced N fertilization. However, in the model AGMEMOD, changes in crop yields did not lead to such land-use changes, but rather to changes in prices and import/export of crop products. We therefore decided to discuss changes in agricultural management that affect SOC stocks in this chapter (Kasparinskis et al. 2025b).

Agricultural intensification is vital for global food security (Ickowitz et al., 2019; Philpott, 2013), but can adversely affect soil resources, notably soil organic carbon (SOC) content (Goidts & van Wesemael, 2007). In Europe SOC losses in response to intensification are widespread and for example Belgium saw a decline of 5.8 t C/ha over 50 years (Goidts & van Wesemael, 2007), and British soils lost approximately 0.08 t C/ha annually from 1970 to 2010 (Muhammed et al., 2018). Barley and maize monocultures in Finland also reported annual SOC reductions of 1 t C/ha and 0.3 t C/ha, respectively (Valkama et al., 2020). These results stress the importance of sustainable agricultural strategies to maintain soil health and carbon storage.

Changes in agricultural practices, particularly the use of monoculture, can significantly impact soil properties and the ecosystem services provided by soils. Prolonged monoculture cultivation has been linked to declines in soil quality and soil organic carbon (SOC) content. Specifically, studies report lower SOC in maize (Loges et al., 2018), wheat (de Cárcer et al., 2019), and potato (Nyawade et al., 2019) monoculture fields compared to crop rotation systems.

The specific crop cultivated also influences SOC levels; for example, potato cultivation reduces SOC because the amount of crop residues left in the field are small (Nyawade et al., 2019). Additionally, differences in carbon accumulation may arise from the characteristics of the crops themselves, as maize, a C₄ plant, contributes less to soil carbon accumulation than wheat, a C₃ plant (Kan et al., 2022). These findings highlight the importance of crop diversity in promoting soil health and carbon storage.

Ecosystem services (ES) of soils are profoundly influenced by human-induced land-use and land cover (LULC) changes. Over the past century, widespread conversion of seminatural grasslands into intensively managed agricultural landscapes has resulted in considerable biodiversity loss and diminished ES provision (Prangel et al., 2023). The push for intensified biomass production often signifies a reduced landscape capacity to deliver essential ecosystem functions, particularly relating to groundwater regulation and soil protection, thereby indicating soil degradation (Baude et al., 2019).

Research by Fang et al. (2023) illustrates that the most significant ES losses are associated with soil erosion, while agricultural productivity represents the largest gain. Rapid agricultural conversion during economic growth is linked to biodiversity loss and increases in carbon emissions, soil erosion, and climate-related challenges. Englund et al. (2020) assessed soil organic carbon (SOC) losses, noting that about one-third of EU landscapes—comprising 70% of total annual crop production—exhibit high to very high SOC depletion. These findings advocate for modifications to land-use practices to mitigate these impacts (Fang et al., 2024).

The establishment of protected areas typically results in increased regulating and cultural ES, while a reduction in agricultural pressure leads to enhanced outcomes across various ecosystem service indicators. Permanent grasslands generally yield superior ES values relative to croplands, except for forage yield (Schils et al., 2022; Schirpke & Tasser, 2021). However, degradation from abandonment or afforestation significantly impairs service provision and biodiversity in these grasslands. Elevated management intensity within permanent grasslands can severely impair multifunctionality, detrimentally affecting biodiversity and climate regulation. Thus, preserving these grasslands is essential for maintaining diverse ecosystem services, as their conversion poses risks to critical functions such as carbon sequestration and water purification (Schils et al., 2022).

2.6. How to assess the impact of reduced nitrogen fertilization on different ecosystem services simultaneously

To assess potential trade-offs of reduced mineral nitrogen (N) fertilization on multiple ecosystem services of soils we applied the SOMMIT Index tool that was developed within the EJP SOIL project SOMMIT for trade-off analysis (Calone et al. 2024). This allows a quantitative assessment of the trade-offs among yields, SOC, N₂O and NO₃, presenting a comprehensive evaluation of reduced N fertilization. We calculated a SOMMIT Index for each NUTS2 region in Europe and for each of the six most important main crops (wheat, maize, barley, rapeseed, sugar beet, potato; Anjum et al. 2025). Our aim was to understand for which of these crops and in which regions/or under which pedoclimatic conditions productivity could be maintained while sustainability could be increased. In such cases the SOMMIT index is high (close to 1). In contrast, low SOMMIT index values (close to 0) indicate conditions under which a reduction in mineral N fertilization poses risks for production and or SOC storage or that only lead to minor reductions in N losses. SOMMIT index values of around 0.5 indicate neither a loss nor a gain in sustainability.

Averaged across all countries the SOMMIT index values were lower for barley and rapeseed compared to other crops, possibly indicating higher risks of reduced N fertilization for these (lower yields, SOC loss). For maize, potato, sugar beet and wheat SOMMIT index values remained higher under the F2F scenario suggesting that a reduction of fertilization rates by 20 % might be feasible. However, spatial variability in SOMMIT index values was large (Figure 4). Regions with high SOMMIT index values could

be identified such as parts of Spain in the case of potato or regions in the Netherlands in the case of maize. In contrast, large parts of Italy and Greece had low SOMMIT index values for barley.

Figure 4. SOMMIT index for six important arable crops presented for each NUTS2 region. Target regions for a reduction in mineral N fertilization were identified based on a very high index (e.g. parts of Spain in the case of potato or parts of the Netherlands in the case of maize). Regions with high risks for yield reductions/and or high SOC losses or regions where N losses remain high despite reduced fertilization have a low index (e.g. large parts of Italy and Greece for barley).

We conclude that a general implementation of reduced N fertilization bears risks for crop production and SOC storage. However, the spatial analysis showed that these risks are not evenly distributed across Europe. Overall NUTS2 regions spanning the entire range of SOMMIT index values could be found from very low to very high. In regions with very low values the risks of a 20 % reduction in mineral N fertilization are high for crop production and SOC storage and/or N losses. In contrast, regions with high SOMMIT index values are regions where these risks are low. These could be focus areas where reduced fertilization could be implemented first. However, additional factors need to be included in future studies, such as the quality of produced goods which is also affected by fertilization rates. Overall, this study improves our understanding of how trade-offs may be accounted for in practice, giving insights that are essential for the effective implementation of the F2F strategy.

2.7. Conclusions

The results of the SIMPLE project indicate that the implementation of the main elements of the F2F policy has advantages and disadvantages. For the main scenario, i.e. a generic 20 % reduction in mineral N fertilisation, there may be significant yield reductions for the major main crops. Such reductions may be associated with reduced product quality and the risk of SOC losses and lower soil fertility. On the other hand, there are significant environmental benefits in terms of reduced N₂O emissions and NO₃ losses, but far from the EU target of -50 %. Lower yields due to reduced fertilisation and higher shares of organic farming may induce land use changes. At the European level, this is considered feasible from the point of view of overall food production, given the current abandoned agricultural land resources, especially in Central and Eastern Europe. Mineral N fertiliser use may also be reduced in response to higher fertiliser prices. Overall, the low price elasticity

indicates that the price of fertilisers will have only a marginal effect on fertiliser use. Also, for dietary changes, the environmental benefits are rather small compared to reduced N fertilisation. The effects of agricultural policies on yields, environmental parameters and their trade-offs are specific to crop type and geographical region, suggesting that policies should be implemented considering the regional context.

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